

CONTEXTUAL FACTORS AND PERSONALITY TRAITS FOR IMPROVED ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS: DIRECTIONS FOR SELF-EMPLOYMENT CAPABILITY ENHANCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to identify the contextual factors and personality traits of the Senior High School students and how these traits affect their entrepreneurial intentions. Specifically, the undertaking tries to examine the (1) significant relationships between the respondents' contextual factors and their entrepreneurial intentions; and (2) significant relationship between the respondents' personality traits and their entrepreneurial intentions. The respondents were all the Senior High School students with a total of 85 students in Bitin Integrated National High School, Bitin Bay, Laguna. Using correlational-descriptive research, the undertaking revealed that the respondents' openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism have significant relationship with their entrepreneurial intentions. Overall, there is statistically significant relationship between respondents' personality traits and their entrepreneurial intentions. Furthermore, 3 out of 10 contextual factors as statistically significant to their entrepreneurial intention these are namely, place of residence, respondents' father's occupation and business they want to engage in. Contrarily, no significant relationship was observed between the respondents' sex, religion, educational exposure, highest educational attainment, academic performance, mother's occupation, academic strand/track and family monthly income. In totality, there is no statistically significant relationship between the respondents' contextual factors and their entrepreneurial intentions.

Keywords: Contextual Factors, Personality Traits, Entrepreneurial Intentions